

REBOOT
EUROPEAN FILM COMPETITIVENESS

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Project: Reviving, Boosting, Optimising and Transforming European Film Competitiveness - REBOOT

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1. PROJECT SUMMARY

This report is part of the European Horizon 2020 REBOOT project (Reviving, Boosting, Optimising and Transforming European Film Competitiveness), which focuses on the European audiovisual sector and its film industry. The REBOOT project aims to connect their strengths, identify and overcome weaknesses, and plan for future competitiveness in the fields of policy, practices and experiences. More concretely, the project's objectives are, on the one hand, to explore the long-standing strengths and pervasive gaps in European audiovisual competitiveness and policies for competitiveness—including ways of 'measuring', 'analyzing' and 'evaluating' the impact of policies and strategic pathways. The project aspires to focus attention on actively preparing for the future by exploring audience preferences and how these are generated, as well as modes of film content production.

The latter are elements which today's youth will carry and engage with in the coming decades as makers and consumers, as well as industry and policy leaders. The project therefore interrogates the 'what is', but also the 'what has been' and 'what will be' through fresh lenses. REBOOT aims to provide a holistic overview of the European film industry, focusing on maximizing its existing strengths while developing strategies and tactics to optimize the potential of European youth audiences, both as emerging viewers and as engaged citizens. Specifically, the project's goals combine several dimensions which reinforce each other but are listed separately (and in no particular order) for analytical purposes: a) increasing support intended to increase young people's engagement with European film; b) strengthening the position of the European Union (EU) in the global audiovisual economy, particularly in light of the rise of video-on-demand; c) supporting cultural diversity in the EU film industry; d) addressing the need for a different understanding of competitiveness and relevant indicators in this context; and e) recognizing and supporting the importance for the EU of film and, more broadly, of the cultural and creative sector as a geopolitical asset.

2. PURPOSE OF THIS DOCUMENT

This document contains Policy Briefs and Recommendations that emerged from WP2 – WP5

The following policy briefs are provided:

Public value as a factor of competitiveness of the European film industry: insights from six European markets	5
Pathway to the Operationalisation of the Common European Data Space for Cultural Heritage: On the Interplay of Cultural Heritage Law and Digital Cultural Assets	20
Developing the EU Film Festival into a two-way event with a clear international cultural relations approach.....	30
The Circulation of European Films in Latin America: Focus on Major Markets and Box Office Performance	39
Lessons from the past: European film industry looks back at thirty years of paradoxes	53

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Policy Brief

January 2025

Public value as a factor of competitiveness of the European film industry: insights from six European markets

Authors: Gentiana Ramadani (UNIVIE), Angeliki Chatziefrimidou (UNIVIE) and Katharine Sarikakis (UNIVIE)

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Who is this aimed at

- EU policy-makers
- national authorities
- industry stakeholders
- national institutions

Key messages

Public value is an important aspect of the European Film Industry (EFI) that represents an evolving framework through which the industry's impact, contributions, and potential to enhance societal well-being can be understood.

Public value in and of the film industry is rooted in active citizen participation and culminates in empowering communities by sharing stories about experiences and the human condition.

Supporting the industry's public value through policy and strategic actions, funding and long-term comprehensive governance of the industry's ecosystem is a crucial factor in strengthening the competitiveness of the EFI.

Competitiveness in the sector goes beyond financial profitability. Instead, competitiveness for the EFI must be understood as a process, which often has roots in the ability to address societal and cultural concerns through storytelling, for which public funding principles and EFI aims align. The process of supporting the EFI through public institutions enables diverse players, from independent producers to smaller companies, to engage in film production and reach global audiences.

Initiatives such as gender equity in production roles, environmentally conscious practices, and multilingual content are essential for societal impact and future audience engagement.

Investments in infrastructure, co-productions, and independent productions stimulate cultural identity, artistic innovation, and societal well-being alongside economic growth.

Overview

The film and audiovisual sector in Europe has long been shaped by public policies aiming at supporting and protecting the EFI, primarily due to the dominant market position of Hollywood and the economic challenges faced by national film industries. European public authorities are driven by

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the need to address cultural and political concerns about image production and distribution (European Audiovisual Observatory, 2004).

Over the past few decades, the EFI has significantly transformed the ways in which competitiveness is defined and pursued. Conversations and interviews with industry experts, many of whom have been active for over 30 years, reveal a remarkable shift in focus. While competitiveness remains a key pillar of the industry, its form has evolved, reflecting changes in priorities and market demands. During the 1980s and 1990s, the industry's primary concern revolved around production. Stakeholders were engaged in discussions about developing and producing films with clear purpose and impact. The emphasis was on the creative and technical dimensions of filmmaking, focusing on the process of crafting stories that could stand out in a competitive landscape. At that time, the notion of competitiveness was narrowly tied to production capabilities, quality, and innovation within the studio and on set. However, beginning in the 2000s, a noticeable shift occurred. The conversation moved beyond production and began to centre on how to reach and engage audiences, and ensure films resonated with diverse viewers. Distribution strategies became a focal point, with stakeholders exploring new ways to connect films with broader and more varied audiences, whether through traditional cinemas or emerging digital platforms. This evolution marked a transition toward a more comprehensive understanding of competitiveness, one that considered not just the act of making films but also the entire value chain from production to distribution and audience engagement¹ (Ramos Arenas, 2025). As the film industry has evolved significantly in recent years, particularly with the blurring of traditional roles due to the emergence of major new players like streaming platforms, today, companies like Netflix, Amazon, and Disney+ are simultaneously producers, distributors, and exhibitors, financing original content, controlling its distribution, and hosting it on their own platforms. This vertical integration allows them to bypass traditional intermediaries, directly influencing market access, content visibility, and audience engagement.

Today, this comprehensive approach to competitiveness recognises the importance of accessibility, cultural relevance, and economic sustainability. The EFI is called to navigate a complex market to succeed: the evolving EU audiovisual and film policy reflects this complex interplay between priorities for cultural diversity, democratic values, and economic imperatives (Michalis 2014). This policy landscape is increasingly shaped by digital transformation, which has opened new

¹ Conversation with Fernando Ramos Arenas in an exchange workshop on behalf of the event: “Reinventing Public Service Media for the Age of Platforms” workshop in Warsaw – Reboot in collaboration with Chanse funded project PSM-AP, Warsaw, Poland (January 22–24, 2025).

opportunities while presenting new challenges, such as the need to remove barriers to digital trade, improve cross-border access to content, and ensure a level playing field among market participants. Strategies integrate innovative distribution models, targeted marketing, and the preservation of cultural heritage to ensure that films reach their intended audiences and leave a lasting impact. These efforts aim to enhance the competitiveness of the EFI and the broader audiovisual sector while safeguarding cultural diversity and promoting innovation across the region (Vlassis 2021).

The European Commission's initiatives, such as the Creative Europe program, emphasise the importance of public funding in bolstering the sector's competitiveness. Such policies recognise that public investment is not merely a financial contribution, but an essential mechanism for fostering industrial growth, creativity, and cultural exchange. Public funds enable filmmakers to experiment with new ideas and narratives, particularly in genres that may not be commercially viable, thus promoting a rich diversity of voices in cinema. Additional initiatives prioritise media literacy and the preservation of Europe's rich film heritage, underscoring the cultural and educational dimensions of EU policies.

In a Europe marked by its rich diversity of nations, cultures, and languages, film production and transnational networks play a key role in fostering cultural unity. While cultural policies were not initially at the forefront of European Union priorities, historical treaties and initiatives have increasingly recognised the significance of these networks for both cultural and political integration (Bondebjerg, 2016).

Public intervention in the industry has taken various forms, particularly in regulating the economic structure of television, which plays a key role in shaping the industry's dynamics. Authorities influence the sector through public funding, regulation of private funding, and imposing investment obligations on broadcasters. Additionally, sectoral aid, which includes direct subsidies, tax relief, preferential credit, and financial guarantees, has been crucial for supporting production and promoting investment. Public policies also include the organisation of practical support for filming, such as film commissions, and film promotion activities like festivals and international marketing efforts. These interventions aim to strengthen the competitiveness of national film industries and foster collaboration across borders. Thus, these transformations in the EFI highlight the importance of adaptability and innovation. By shifting from a production-focused model to one that prioritizes audience connection and market reach, the industry has embraced new opportunities for growth and cultural exchange. As part of this evolution, the focus has expanded to include priorities such

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as public value, and recognising the essential role of cultural production in enriching society (Sarikakis, Ramadani, Chatziefrimidou, Juengst, 2024).

The concept of 'public value,' introduced by Mark Moore (1995), refers to creating a legitimate, sustainable, and efficient contribution that addresses societal needs. While widely used in the public sector (Bracci et al., 2019; Bryson et al., 2014; Van der Wal et al., 2015), its application in the film industry is less developed. There is limited research on how public value is assessed within the film sector, especially regarding its impact on society and the measurable outcomes. However, public institutions have been at the forefront of this shift, providing important support and boosting collaboration to meet the changing needs of filmmakers and audiences alike. Their efforts have ensured that the EFI remains vibrant, competitive, and capable of navigating the challenges of a rapidly evolving global landscape. Public support for the arts and culture, including film, is fundamental to preserving the public value inherent in cultural production. Cultural and artistic endeavours, which often carry significant social, historical, and aesthetic importance, rely heavily on public funding to thrive. Hence the public value of the EFI is widely recognised through the practical support as part of public policy in Europe. Without this support, many forms of artistic expression might struggle to survive or remain accessible only to an elite minority (Dickinson & Harvey, 2005; Pratt, 1997, 2005). Since public funds provide strong support for the market, they play a crucial role in enabling diverse and inclusive cultural representation. By ensuring that society's many voices are heard and reflected in creative industries, public funding helps to promote equity and inclusivity. This support manifests in several ways, from direct subsidies for filmmakers to financial aid for cultural institutions and initiatives. Public funding not only sustains a diverse cultural ecosystem, but also makes cultural experiences more accessible to the general public, breaking barriers and democratizing access to the arts. In doing so, it reinforces the public value of the film industry, aligning its evolution with broader societal goals and ensuring its role as a key driver of cultural, social, and economic enrichment. Public intervention is often considered necessary to correct market failures and to meet these cultural policy goals (European Audiovisual Observatory, 2024). This intervention helps ensure that the cultural sector is supported in ways the market alone might not provide, enabling the promotion of broader cultural values.

Evaluating public value in the film industry

First the concept of public value, as introduced in 1995, emerged not as a rigid definition, but as a fluid ideal. Moore envisioned public managers as stewards, tasked with fostering and expanding the value that benefits society. Their decisions, rooted in the public good, aim to enhance the

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effectiveness of public institutions. Over time, this vision has evolved into a broader understanding, one that emphasizes the artful and purposeful use of public resources, shaping them to serve the collective interest and uphold the shared values that bind communities together. Based on how public value in the film sector is understood or studied, in this document with an analysis of six selected film markets currently operating in Europe, presents a comprehensive look at the public institutions supporting the sector within five categories: public service media, national film institutions, ministries or departments responsible for film, academic institutions, and film festivals. While these institutions support and finance the film sector according to the national regulations, the majority of their funding is based on economic formulas and financial grant schemes. Social and cultural aspects are also integrated into these schemes with considerable weight. Although states are increasingly taking cultural impacts into account when designing fiscal incentives, this process is still in its early stages and does not yet provide sufficient (comparable) data to allow for an in-depth analysis of these impacts.

However, a clearer way to measure the public value in the film industry's budgeting is possible by focusing on employment. By examining the direct impact of the film and audiovisual industries, it is also possible to assess the indirect impacts on output and employment. Thus, the analysis of the impact of public value in the film sector begins by focusing on incentive schemes, highlighting key characteristics such as production spend, which reflects the level of financial support provided to the industry, and employment growth, measured by the number of jobs created as a result of these incentives. Furthermore, the analysis looks at a selection of films funded by these institutions, with particular attention to the themes and subjects of their production. By evaluating these factors, it is assessed how effectively these incentives affect both the economic and cultural development of the sector. In Europe, three primary types of film production incentives are used: tax shelters, rebates, and tax credits (Audiovisual Observatory, December 2014).

Tax shelters allow high net-worth individuals or firms to invest in qualifying productions and deduct these investments from their tax liabilities, while still being able to benefit from long-term profits, which are taxed upon receipt. Rebates, on the other hand, are based on production spending, reimbursing a percentage of eligible expenses after the production is completed and audited. These are funded directly by the state. Tax credits function similarly to rebates by reimbursing a percentage of production costs through a predetermined formula, but instead of being paid from a state fund, the incentive is deducted from the producer's tax liabilities, with any excess refunded in cash.

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These schemes are designed to incentivise investment in film productions by offering financial relief, with each having distinct methods of distribution and calculation. A brief overview of the data underscores the crucial role of public institutions and funding mechanisms in supporting the film industry across Europe, as exemplified by the tax schemes outlined in Table 1.

Country	Rebate Details
France	30% rebate (max €30 million per project)
Spain	30% for the first million, 25% for the rest; 50% in Canary Islands
Belgium	42% rebate, €465 million in 2019 for film/TV
Austria	€5 million allocated for local and international projects in 2020
Poland	30% cash rebate, €45 million attracted between 2019-2021
Greece	40% cash rebate, €100 million allocated between 2018-2021

Table 1. The table presents data analysed, work conducted by the authors, based on the Sarikakis et al. (2024) "Governance and Public Value Report - Producing Value through the Moving Images: An Analysis of Public Value and its Cultural Contribution to the Strength and Competitiveness of the European Film Sector" part of the Horizon Europe project REBOOT.

Key findings

Austria's public support for the film sector is assessed across several dimensions: economic, cultural, societal, and democratic value. Economically, public funding from organizations like the Austrian Film Institute (ÖFI) and the Austrian Television Fund plays a crucial role in supporting film production while also stimulating other sectors, such as tourism, by showcasing Austria's locations and culture internationally. As noted by industry representatives, public funding serves as a direct investment in the film industry and contributes to economic competitiveness² (Goeschl and Deutsch-

² Monique Goeschl and Markus Deutsch are representatives of the trade association Film and Music Austria (FAMA) in the Austrian Federal Economic Chamber (WKÖ) and were interviewed in September 2024.

interview 2024). In 2023, the Austrian Film Institute (ÖFI) operated with a total budget of €36.5 million, comprising €21 million for selective funding and €15.5 million allocated to the newly established location incentive scheme, ÖFI+. A total of 187 projects received support that year, reflecting ÖFI's commitment to fostering Austria's film industry (Report, ÖFI, 2024).

Culturally, Austria's film funding policies aim to preserve and promote the country's cultural identity. The Austrian Film Institute and the Art Section of the Federal Chancellery support projects that reflect Austria's cultural and artistic diversity, including experimental films that would not thrive in the commercial market. As Peter Schernhuber³ (interview, 2024) highlights, public funding ensures the distinctiveness of Austrian cinema by promoting films with unique artistic qualities that strengthen national identity. On the societal front, public funding is evaluated based on its role in supporting films that engage with critical societal issues such as historical memory, migration, and cultural diversity. Projects funded by the Austrian Film Institute and the Art Section encourage public discourse on these topics, enhancing the social relevance of Austrian cinema (based on the public list available). This highlights the role of film as a platform for public dialogue, contributing to a more inclusive and culturally conscious society.

Belgium's film industry exemplifies a well-balanced approach to fostering economic growth, cultural preservation, and social inclusion through a combination of public funding, tax incentives, and regional support. Public broadcasters such as RTBF and VRT are instrumental in driving this progress. RTBF, for instance, invests a minimum of €30 million annually in local productions through co-productions and pre-purchase contracts, while VRT provides extensive backing for filmmakers through production orders, development funds, and partnerships. These investments not only stimulate the film production value chain and create employment but also help Belgian films achieve international recognition and highlight themes central to national identity. Economic contributions are further bolstered by the Belgian Tax Shelter, a fiscal incentive introduced in 2002. Offering a 40% tax deduction for investments in eligible audiovisual works, this initiative has significantly increased private sector involvement, ensuring the financing of local productions and attracting international projects (Wallimage, n.d.). Complementary to this, regional film funds such as Wallimage, with an annual budget of €5.5 million, Screen Brussels at €3 million, and the Flanders Audiovisual Fund (VAF) at €4.5 million, have a critical role in supporting regional productions, co-productions, and infrastructure development. As per the societal aspect, Belgium's film industry has made remarkable strides in engaging communities and cultivating talent. Prestigious institutions

³ Peter Schernhuber is head of the Film Department at the Federal Ministry for Arts, Culture, the Civil Service and Sport in Austria and was interviewed in September 2024.

such as INSAS, RITCS, KASK, and LUCA School of Arts provide cutting-edge education in filmmaking, equipping young professionals with the skills to succeed in a competitive industry. Film festivals further enhance accessibility and cultural engagement. With around 35 festivals annually, these events showcase a wide range of genres and bring specialized films to underserved regions. In 2022⁴, for example, Flemish films attracted over 1.8 million cinema-goers, reflecting the growing interest in local productions and their capacity to connect with diverse audiences. Culturally, Belgium's policies ensure that its cinematic identity remains distinct and impactful. Mechanisms such as the CCA Cinema Decree emphasize cultural contributions as a key criterion for financial support, ensuring that films reflect and preserve Belgian and European heritage. Language-specific funding further reinforces linguistic and cultural diversity, particularly in the French-speaking and Flemish communities.

The Spanish film industry exemplifies a well-coordinated network of public institutions and financial frameworks that can generate significant public value. The sector benefits from a robust combination of national and regional support systems, targeted initiatives, and comprehensive policies that nurture both the cultural and economic dimensions of filmmaking. It showcases the effective synergy between public institutions, financial incentives, and supportive legislation, generating significant cultural and economic value. With robust national and regional support, including €50 million in direct subsidies from Spain's Instituto de la Cinematografía y de las Artes Audiovisuales (ICAA)⁵ and tax incentives like those in the Canary Islands, Spain has become a global audiovisual hub. Similarly, ICEX Spain Trade and Investment promotes Spanish audiovisual productions internationally, with an annual budget of €130 million (ICEX, 2024)⁶.

The sector also thrives through cultural diplomacy, with festivals and international successes like *La Casa de Papel* elevating its global influence. The combination of public investment, a strategic legislative framework, and strong international promotion reinforces Spain's position as a leader in the audiovisual industry.

The French film industries deliver significant public value through job creation, economic growth, and cultural export. Key players such as France Télévisions, Arte, and France 24 contribute notably to both direct and indirect employment. France Télévisions, with over 10,000 employees, invested €285 million in drama production in 2023, making it the largest investor in French drama (France

⁴ Flanders Audiovisual Fund (VAF). (2024). <https://www.vaf.be/>

⁵ Ministerio de Cultura y Deporte

⁶ Acción Cultural Española, 2024; Spain Audiovisual Hub, 2023

Télévisions, n.d.), while Arte, with 500 employees, focuses on European cultural programming and co-productions, boosting both job creation and cultural diversity (Arte, 2023). France 24, employing 1,800 people, broadcasts to over 355 million households globally, strengthening France's cultural diplomacy (France Médias Monde, 2022). These organizations also support related sectors like digital media and translation services. Together, their substantial financial investments, such as France Télévisions' €3.5 billion in total revenue and Arte's €287 million, illustrate how public institutions drive economic benefits, international influence, and employment within the broader creative industries, reinforcing France's position as a leader in global cultural production.

Data shows that in 2022, **Poland's film industry** made a substantial economic impact, with an investment of 2,528 million PLN (US \$569 million) resulting in an economic output of 8,671 million PLN (US \$1,952 million) Materska-Samek, 2023, p. 28. The Gross Value Added (GVA) from production was 3,416 million PLN (US \$769 million), reflecting the additional economic value generated. The sector also created 21,021 full-time equivalent jobs, highlighting its contribution to employment.

Key Recommendations

- 1) Enhance the collection of basic data regarding film and TV sector incentives. There is a need for more granular and comprehensive data from national institutions and agencies to better assess the impact of these schemes. Specifically, data collection should be expanded to include, more detailed breakdown of projects benefiting from incentives, including genre, distribution channels, and audience reach; more precise tracking of funding allocations, distinguishing between national and international productions; information on co-production structures and cross-border collaborations; data on long-term economic and cultural impact, such as job creation, diversity in storytelling, and sustainability of funded projects; essential data should include details about the projects benefiting from these schemes, such as project lists, funding amounts, countries of origin, budgets, and financing structures. This type of data is currently lacking in countries like Greece and Poland, while Austria, France and Spain have a more structured reporting system.
- 2) Additionally, sector-specific data, including the number of productions, production spending, employee numbers, and investments in facilities, should be gathered. Data on both direct and indirect economic impacts, as well as the fiscal impact (gross and net benefit/cost for the state), is crucial for comprehensive evaluation. To collect this

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- information, collaboration with national statistics agencies and the European Audiovisual Observatory would be valuable in strengthening the work on structural business statistics.
- 3) Develop metrics to evaluate Public Value impact and introduce comprehensive tools for assessing and measuring the societal and cultural impacts of public value initiatives. These metrics should extend beyond economic indicators to encompass educational outreach, audience engagement, and contributions to cultural diversity and sustainability.
 - 4) Balance Economic Competitiveness with Cultural Diversity. Policies fostering competitiveness in the film industry do not overshadow the need for cultural diversity and originality. Policymakers should consider funding schemes and regulatory frameworks that support industry growth while safeguarding cultural diversity. This includes allocating resources to independent and underrepresented voices, incentivizing local storytelling, and ensuring that market-driven strategies do not marginalize diverse content. Public value initiatives within the film industry need greater coherence and integration across different governance levels. Policymakers should establish unified frameworks to better coordinate efforts, streamline funding mechanisms, and ensure public value considerations are consistently embedded in decision-making processes.
 - 5) Support for emerging talent and innovation through public funding. It should prioritize nurturing newcomers and diverse voices in the film industry through targeted mentorship programs, competitions, and grants. This support should also extend to innovative and experimental projects that may lack commercial appeal but contribute significantly to cultural and societal enrichment.

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Policy Brief

January 2025

Pathway to the Operationalisation of the Common European Data Space for Cultural Heritage: On the Interplay of Cultural Heritage Law and Digital Cultural Assets

Authors: Caterina Sganga (SSSA) and Pelin Turan (SSSA)

REBOOT (www.thereboot-project.eu) has received funding from European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 101094769.

Who is this aimed at

- EU and national policy- and law-makers
- Industrial stakeholders
- Cultural heritage institutions

Key messages

The Common European Data Space for Cultural Heritage (hereinafter 'CHDS') was launched by the European Union (hereinafter 'EU') in 2021 as one of the fourteen domain/sector-specific data spaces setting up the Common European Data Space (hereinafter 'CEDs') promoted by the European Strategy for Data (Communication COM(2011) 140 final Communication COM(2020) 263 final). The CHDS aims at accelerating the digitisation, online availability, reuse and digital preservation of diverse forms of European cultural assets (i.e. tangible, intangible, movable, immovable, natural, born-digital, analogue) forming the cultural heritage (hereinafter 'CH') of the EU Member States (Recommendation (EU) 2021/1970).

Audiovisual/cinematographic content constitutes one of the key areas of the CHDS due to the low rate of digitisation of this category of CH assets and the risk of deterioration of the media on which such cultural content is fixated (Recommendation (EU) 2021/1970, Recommendation 2011/711/EU, Recommendation 2005/865/CE). However, the digitisation, reuse and cross-border flow of digital audiovisual/cinematographic content is a complicated task due to, on the one hand, the distribution of competences between the EU and the Member States and, on the other hand, the bundle of overlapping (if not clashing) EU and national legal regimes governing the digitisation, online availability and reuse, and digital preservation of audiovisual/cinematographic content.⁷

The European Commission (EC) referred to the enactment of an implementing act for the CHDS in the near future (Commission Decision C(2021) 4647 final). The successful realisation of this plan and the population of the new data space with audiovisual/cinematographic content not only urges the adoption of a robust roadmap that could facilitate data transfers among key stakeholders/market actors, but also requires a meticulous assessment of the legal tools and incentive mechanisms

⁷ For the copyright-related aspects related to the operationalisation of the CHDS, please see the first part of this policy brief series. See: Sarikakis, K., Ramadani, G., Chatziefraimidou, A., Juengst, J., Psychogiopoulou, E., Samaras, A., Comerma, L., Vlassis, A., Riga, D., Sganga, C., Turan, P., Lähdesmäki, T., & Hiltunen, K. (2024). Policy briefings deriving from WP2-5. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10605192>.

available and to be provided in order to enable the digitisation of such content and data transfers in a reliable and interoperable information technology (IT) infrastructure.

This document, which constitutes the second part of the policy brief series dedicated to the operationalisation of the CHDS, addresses the cultural heritage law-related aspects of the data-sharing practices concerning the digitisation and transfers of digital(ised) audiovisual/cinematographic content.⁸

Introduction

The CHDS constitutes a landmark initiative in the EU cultural and digital policies and agenda since the adoption of the Lisbon strategy in 2000. This strategy launched the transition of the EU into a knowledge-based society and data-agile economy in parallel to a wave of digitisation endeavours targeting European CH assets (Communication COM(2001) 140 final Communication COM(2002) 263 final).

The New European Agenda for Cultural Heritage, adopted in 2018 in the European Year of Cultural Heritage, elevated CH to one of the top priorities of the EU's digital policies and advocated for the digitisation and circulation of European artworks across Europe (Communication COM(2018) 267 final). The EU-wide efforts to enhance the digitisation and online accessibility of CH assets, eventually, paved the way for integrating the Union's digital policies concerning CH into the EU's flagship initiative - the CEDS.

Launched in 2018, the CEDS aims to unleash the potential of the extensive volume of data collected and stored within the EU by facilitating the free flow and efficient use of such data across Europe (Communication COM(2018) 232 final, Communication COM(2020) 66 final). Envisaged as 'a seamless digital area', or a smoothly operating *single market for data*, the CEDS would realise cross-border and cross-sectoral transfers of a multitude of types of data with different levels of intensity through a trustworthy and secure IT infrastructure (Communication COM(2018) 232 final, Communication COM(2020) 66 final). The types of data referred to in this context include but are not limited to personal and non-personal, public- and private-sector, publicly-held and privately-held, publicly-funded, machine-generated, research-related, and dynamic data.

⁸ This policy brief stems from the research conducted for a prospective publication, entitled "Common European Data Space for Cultural Heritage: Is the European Union Taking the 'High Road' from 'A Single Access Point' to 'A Single Market for Data' for Digital Cultural Content?", co-authored by Pelin Turan and Caterina Sganga, which has been presented by the co-authors at the EPIP 2024 Conference co-organised by and held in September 2024 at the premises of Scuola Superiore Sant'Anna and the University of Pisa.

As one of the domain/sector-specific data spaces incorporating the CEDS, the CHDS envisions a single digital space facilitating the sharing of born-digital and digitised CH assets, including works of European film heritage (Recommendation (EU) 2021/1970). Nevertheless, the limited success of the EU Member States in digitising audiovisual/cinematographic content necessitates the collaboration of several stakeholders/market actors to map the needs of the CH sector/domain and to assess to what extent the current EU and national legal regimes might be of help to realise the CHDS ambitions.

Statement of the problem

The launch of the CHDS space revolutionised the legal discourse centred around CH assets, placing them at the intersection of copyright law, data law, and cultural heritage law, which are legal disciplines originating from disparate policy objectives and evolved independently by following different paths. Standing at the crossroads of these three bodies of law, the challenges faced by the CHDS are multi-faceted and require multi-disciplinary approaches to help unfold their layers, while unveiling the policy and legislative gaps that necessitate action at the Union and national levels.

The complications imposed by cultural heritage law upon the operationalisation of the CHDS are two-pronged.

On the one hand, the establishment of a digital infrastructure opening the access to and reuse of multiple categories of CH assets – including those of audiovisual and cinematographic content – to public bodies, citizens and businesses for both commercial and non-commercial purposes requires a common perception of what constitutes European film heritage and an EU-wide standard in selecting and digitising the assets to be used to populate the CHDS. Nevertheless, the limited EU competence in matters concerning culture and CH hinders any harmonisation endeavours at the Union level, leaving the regulation of this area to the discretion of Member States. Article 167 of the Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union (hereinafter ‘TFEU’) holds that the EU ‘shall contribute to the flowering of the cultures of Member States, while (...) bringing the common cultural heritage to the fore’. In this sense, the EU’s competence and role are limited to encouraging cooperation across the Union and, if necessary, supporting and supplementing the national actions, such as dissemination of culture, preservation and safeguarding of CH, and cultural exchanges of a non-commercial nature (TFEU, Article 167(2)). Whereas the EU is given the power to adopt incentive measures to achieve these goals, Article 167(5) TFEU clarifies that such efforts cannot result in ‘harmonisation of the law and regulations of the Member States’. This implies that the

operationalisation of the CHDS heavily depends on the different national views of CH embraced by disparate Member States.

On the other hand, recent trends in the international and regional policy-making and norm-setting forums show a positive shift from a 'static' depiction to a 'dynamic' understanding of CH (Faro Convention, Article 2(a), Communication COM(2018) 267 final). Emphasising the 'constant evolution' of the values, beliefs, knowledge and traditions that form CH, these instruments also enable the consideration of not only 'old' works that have fallen into the public domain but also of 'new' works protected by copyright in the context of CH. Such a broad articulation of CH, nevertheless, requires guidance on the interplay of national CH laws with the EU and national copyright regimes – especially given that the in-copyright and public domain status of CH assets plays a crucial role in the EU data laws applicable to the sharing of digital(ised) CH assets (Directive (EU) 2019/1024, Art. 1(2)(c); Regulation (EU) 2022/868, Art. 2(11)).⁹

Policy recommendations

- 1) The successful deployment of the CHDS primarily depends on a shared understanding of CH and a harmonised selection of assets to be digitised for the purposes of a data space dedicated to CH. To achieve this goal, **the EU shall adopt soft law instruments to guide the Member States through the identification and selection of CH assets to be digitised for the CHDS**, whilst taking into consideration the distribution of powers, and without prejudicing Member States' discretion to regulate the legal regime applicable to national CH in light of national cultural priorities and policies.
- 2) Likewise, for the successful deployment of the CHDS, the EU shall mentor and monitor the digitisation of CH asserts by collecting **empirical evidence** via comprehensive studies, which could map **the past and ongoing CH digitisation endeavours of the Member States** and develop, on this basis, **codes of best practices to engage in such digitisation projects vis-à-vis the experiential knowledge held by the Member States and their competent bodies**.
- 3) The population of the CHDS with audiovisual/cinematographic content urges **clarification of the EU vision and plans on the interplay of such content with the CHDS**. At the time being, the information disseminated by the EC does not go beyond the need to digitise

⁹ The data law-related aspects of the operationalisation of the CHDS are to be analysed in the context of the third part of this policy brief series and will be consolidated into Deliverable 7.14 due in Month 36 of the REBOOT project's life-cycle.

audiovisual/cinematographic content. Nevertheless, the feasibility of enabling online access to and reuse of digital(ised) audiovisual/cinematographic content requires further clarification on the EC's expectations from the Member States and the means to promote and enable the reuse of such content in line with the EU data economy goals (e.g. boosting data-based innovation, goods and services).

- 4) Last but not least, the EU shall introduce **incentive mechanisms** to gather **empirical evidence** aimed at mapping and understanding how copyright, cultural heritage and data regimes in different Member States **interact over national CH assets**. The mechanisms adopted at the national level to cope with the intricacies of this interplay could shed light on the need for further legislative interventions in areas that fall under the scope of the EU competences, or soft law instruments in areas that are subject to the discretion of Member States.

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Policy Brief

January 2025

Developing the EU Film Festival into a two-way event with a clear international cultural relations approach

Authors: Tuuli Lähdesmäki (JYU), Mafalda Dâmaso (EUR), Kaisa Hiltunen (JYU), Ruken Doğu Erdede (KHAS), Elif Akçalı (KHAS), Melis Behlil (KHAS)

Reviewers:

REBOOT (www.thereboot-project.eu) has received funding from European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 101094769.

Who is this aimed at

- Officials of the European External Action Service (EEAS) and EU delegations; staff and representatives of EU Member States' embassies, consulates and cultural institutions; Cineuropa managers; local curators and film festival representatives who work with EU delegations to organise EU film festivals.

Key messages

The EU Film Festival (EUFF) is an important tool for developing cultural relations between EU Member States and third countries. The European Commission has already recognised the strategic importance of the festival in its 2016 Communication "Towards an EU strategy for international cultural relations" (EC, 2016, p. 14). The EUFF has great potential to strengthen two-way exchanges between local and European film professionals, while promoting the competitiveness of film industries in Europe and third countries through increased cooperation and co-productions. Previous research has also recommended more negotiations on co-productions and the screening of co-produced films at festivals, as they attract audiences by involving local creators (Helly & Chandran, 2023, p. 21). The EUFF could be further developed by clarifying its overall objectives for all stakeholders involved in the organisation of the festival, by improving two-way exchanges and integrating the festival into broader public diplomacy efforts, by supporting the organisation of side events and expanding the film repository managed by Cineuropa, and by increasing the overall financial support for the festival.

Introduction

To explore the different rationales and organisational challenges behind the EUFF, we conducted a combined desk research and qualitative content analysis of interviews with EEAS officials and EUFF organisers in eight non-EU countries that hosted the festival in 2023, namely Argentina, Canada, Chile, Indonesia, the Republic of South Africa, Türkiye, the United Kingdom and Vietnam. The desk research data consisted of various grey literature, such as communications, reports and festival catalogues, and feedback responses from festival organisers in 27 countries collected by Cineuropa in 2023. The research also included an analysis of the content of the most screened films and the ways in which they represented cultural diversity and other EU values. Finally, the results were explored vis-à-vis the EEAS's approach to strategic communication.

Statement of the problem

Over the past decade, the EU has refined its external relations policies by emphasising bottom-up activities, people-to-people links, dialogue and mutual exchange. However, such an approach to international cultural relations (Murray & Lamonica, 2021) has not been consistently incorporated into all EU policy discourses and guidelines. This situation poses multiple challenges for cultural actors, who must navigate the demands of an as yet unfamiliar policy and its complex governance model in order to serve ambitious, long-term foreign policy goals (Dâmaso, 2021, p. 9). Previous research has shown that, in practice, the EU's foreign policy lacks a coherent doctrine at world level and "coordination could be improved at different levels [...] or through better exchange of information between the EEAS and the EU Delegations" (EP, 2022, p. 17).

In the case of the EUFF, this situation is exacerbated by its governance, which requires the cooperation of EU delegations with the national institutes of EU Member States. The managers of the EUFF programmes must therefore aim for success in the face of competing policies and approaches. Indeed, a similar point was made in the external evaluation of the EUFF commissioned by the European Commission. In it, experts identified the need "to fully align the action with future policy priorities, presentation and debate of the results of this evaluation in the short-term OMC [Open Method Coordination] group on EU international cultural relations, to provide a clearer strategic level of ambition and guidance to film festivals writ large" (Helly & Chandran, 2023, p.15). Film is an important industry at the crossroads of the EU's commercial and external relations interests. The main objective of the EUFF is not explicitly to make a profit. However, it is an implicit tool to promote and increase the visibility of European film.

Existing Policy Gap

The European Commission's Communication on the EU Strategy for International Cultural Relations proposed the creation of a new funding scheme for EU delegations to organise the EUFF (EC, 2016). The idea was based on a feasibility study which found that more than half of EU delegations are involved in organising film festivals and other film events that promote the EU, showcase European culture and use film as a diplomatic tool (EC, 2015, p. 6). However, special support was deemed necessary as "a number of obstacles prevent the diversity and excellence of European films from being shown in the best conditions in many third countries: lack of professionalism, limited budgets and shortage of human resources" (EC, 2015, p. 6). Our research highlights similar practical shortcomings, such as the lack of film expertise in the EU delegations and embassies. The local

festival organisations often compensate for this, but in some cases all the organising is done by the EU delegation.

The EUFF guidelines and funding criteria refer to multiple diplomatic approaches with arguably contradictory underpinnings. Our research underlines the need to sharpen the festival's diplomatic purpose by taking the international cultural relations approach more seriously and consistently into account in the EUFF guidelines, funding criteria and communication, and by better informing all EUFF stakeholders about it.

Similar observations and suggestions are contained in the external evaluation of the EUFF commissioned by the European Commission. It notes that EUFF programme managers must strive for success in the face of competing policies and approaches, and that there is therefore a need to "provide a clearer strategic level of ambition and guidance to film festivals writ large" (Helly & Chandran, 2023, p.15).

Recently, the President of the European Commission requested from the European Commissioner for International Partnerships that the EU takes "a more assertive approach in aligning its interests with its partnerships in a more contested and unstable world" (EC, 2024, p. 5). Our research suggests that strengthening the links between the implementation of the EUFF and the international cultural relations approach is compatible with such an alignment – as long as EU actors avoid an instrumentalising logic, continue to demonstrate consistency between rhetoric and action, and prioritise long-term relationships and audience-building efforts.

Policy recommendations

Our research led to several policy implications, which we summarise below.

- 1) **Communicate EUFF objectives continuously:** Clearly define and communicate the objectives of the EUFF to EU Member States in order to build consensus and shared ownership, highlighting the importance of mutuality and the need to eschew instrumentalism.
- 2) **Frame the EUFF within broader public diplomacy efforts:** Better emphasise and clarify for festival organisers the international cultural relations approach in the implementation of the EUFF.

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- 3) **Focus on shared values:** Promote shared values rather than exclusively "EU values", avoiding the perception of a neo-colonial approach.
 - 4) **Support the engagement of independent film professionals and cultural workers:** Financial support for independent professionals (both European and from third countries) is crucial for their engagement. Such support is in line with the promotion of European values such as diversity and equality.
 - 5) **Strengthen co-productions:** Strengthen existing EU funding for co-productions between European and third countries and prioritise small-scale projects with local professionals and markets to foster deeper collaboration.
 - 6) **Improve two-way exchanges and highlight side events:** Develop the EUFF to better support two-way exchanges between EU and non-EU film professionals, allowing visits by non-EU professionals to the EU, supporting the screening of non-EU films at film festivals in Europe, aiming for the systematic inclusion of local films in the EUFF programme to promote balance and inclusion, and transforming side-events into dialogues, supporting co-learning, collaboration and co-productions, and using films as a basis for discussions on common challenges.
 - 7) **Develop tailored audience engagement:** Develop strategies to engage with existing and new audiences, and improve festival design accordingly.
 - 8) **Address diversity and representation in communication materials:** Address diversity in communications materials to better reflect societal values and inclusivity.
 - 9) **Increase funding for Cineuropa and Delegations:** Provide more financial support to EU Delegations and Cineuropa to increase the number and diversity of films in the repository and at the festivals and to cover costs in low-income markets.

10) Consider broader indicators in implementation monitoring: Use non-quantitative and non-market indicators to measure the impact of the EUFF, including cultural and social outcomes, both in Cineuropa's collection of information and when assessing the implementation of the festival, avoiding a short-termist analysis of results.

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Policy Brief

January 2025

The Circulation of European Films in Latin America: Focus on Major Markets and Box Office Performance

Authors: Luis A. Albornoz (UC3M), M^a Trinidad García Leiva (UC3M), Isabela Vargas Miranda (UC3M)

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Who is this aimed at

- EU policy-makers
- National authorities
- Industry stakeholders

Key messages

Despite strong cultural, linguistic, and historical ties between Latin America and Europe, the circulation of European films in Latin America is limited and its economic impact unknown. To address this, several key actions should be considered. Firstly, existing support programs for European film distribution and promotion in Latin America should be reviewed and simplified to enhance their accessibility to distributors. Reviving initiatives like Europa Cinema Mundus, which fostered theatrical programming and cross-border exchange, could significantly boost this effort. Secondly, co-production agreements between countries should be revised to align with current industry practices. Furthermore, establishing a central database containing information on co-production agreements and support programs would significantly improve access to resources and facilitate cross-country exchange. Finally, fostering stronger cooperation with publicly managed exhibition windows would enhance the presence and prominence of European films in the region. In short, these measures aim to improve the circulation and, in turn, the potential economic viability of European films in Latin America by simplifying support programs, modernizing coproduction agreements, enhancing information access, and supporting stronger partnerships in film exhibitions with public institutions.

Introduction

Latin America is a key region for the European film industry due to its strong cultural, historical, and linguistic ties to Europe, particularly with Spain and Portugal, and, to a lesser extent, France, Italy, Germany, and Netherlands. The region also plays a vital role in the global film market, hosting prestigious international film festivals and representing some of the largest markets worldwide in terms of admissions numbers. Despite these connections, several barriers hinder the circulation of EU films, including regulatory challenges, and the overwhelming dominance of Hollywood blockbusters in the region. This policy brief is based on a study conducted in the REBOOT project aimed at examining the views of international film professionals towards the European Film Industry (EFI) in six international markets.

The UC3M research team focused on Latin America, more specifically, in the three countries with the most developed film industries: Argentina, Brazil and Mexico. These countries have the largest

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cinematographic industries in the region, representing more than 80% of the fiction films produced (Rodríguez, 2020). Additionally, Mexico and Brazil have considerable home audiences, with Mexico being the fourth largest market in the world in terms of tickets sold, while Brazil ranks ninth. Whereas Argentina is the tenth largest market globally by feature film production ([Kanzler & Fioroni, 2024](#)). Using existing market data and preliminary findings from interviews conducted by the team as a starting point, the objective of this brief is to provide an overview of European films' performance in theaters in Argentina, Brazil, and Mexico, along with basic recommendations.

Context

A recent study by the European Audiovisual Observatory revealed that between 2014 and 2023 Latin America¹⁰ accounted for 5% of total admissions to European films followed by the US and Asia, each with 5%, while Europe accounted for an overwhelming 82%. Focusing exclusively on 2023, non-European markets accounted for only 26% of export admissions¹¹, a notable decline compared to previous years, during which the market share of admissions to European films consistently fluctuated around 50%. Out of the said 26%, Latin America accounted for 10%, followed by North America with 7%, Asia with 4% and other markets with 5% ([Fioroni, 2024](#)).

¹⁰ Countries covered in the study mentioned representing Latin America are Argentina, Brazil, Chile, Colombia, Mexico, and Venezuela.

¹¹ Export admissions refer to ticket sales in all markets outside the domestic market, including those in co-producing countries where the financial contributions are minority

Table 1: General Data

	Argentina	Brazil	Mexico
Population 2023 (million)	46.8	204.2	131.2
GDP per capita 2023 (USD)	13.297	10.413	13.804
Gross box office 2023 (million USD)*	168.4	447.9	832.0
Admissions 2023 (million)	40.6	114.1	218.4
Average ticket price 2023 (USD)	4.1	3.9	3.8
Average admissions per capita 2023	0.9	0.6	1.7
Screens 2023	954	3.468	7.389
National market shares 2023	7.6%	3.2%	4.0%

Source: European Audiovisual Observatory - Focus - World Film Market Trends 2024

(*): Estimate based on data provided by Observatorio Iberoamericano do Audiovisual, ICAA, ANCINE and IMCINE to the European Audiovisual Observatory.

In terms of cinema attendance, Brazil saw an increase of 19.7% in 2023, reaching 114 million tickets. Still the market share of European films based on ticket sales was only 1.8% (2.097.690 tickets), domestic titles took 3.2% (3.701.853), while US titles accounted for 87% of the market (99.201.177) ([Ancine, 2023](#)). A similar pattern occurred in Mexico: cinema attendance increased by 26.2% in 2023, with 218 million tickets sold corresponding to 64% of 2019 figures ([Kanzler & Fioroni, 2024](#)). Out of those, Europe accounted for 2.3% of the market (5.016.683), domestic films took 4.19% (9.157.699 tickets) and the US represented 90% (196.542.936) ([Imcine, 2023](#)). In Argentina, a total of 40.6 million tickets were sold marking a significant increase compared to the previous year's figure of 34.6 million. Out of this figure, national films achieved a market share of 7.6% (3,089,600) ([Kanzler & Fioroni, 2024](#)). Since 2022 INCAA has not released its annual report, meaning there is no official data on market share by country of origin. Nevertheless, the Panorama Iberoamericano 2024 report provided market share based on cinema attendance for the Top -100 films in 2023, indicating European films at 1.7% (717.200), US films at 89.3% (37.004.473), and national films at 6.7% (2.793.176) ([Egeda, 2024](#)).

When considering solely the number of European films released in each market, European cinema appears to have a stronger performance. In Brazil, out of the 709 films exhibited in 2023, 105 (that is 14.8% of the total) were European, 186 were American (26,2%) and 271 were national titles

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(38.2%) ([Ancine, 2023](#)). In Mexico, Europe released 110 films while the US released 143 films; 95 were Mexican ([Imcine, 2023](#)). In Argentina, out of the 420 films exhibited in 2023, 204 were national films while 222 were foreign films ([Egeda, 2024](#)). As previously stated, an official breakdown of the number of European and US films exhibited in Argentina in 2023 has not been published by INCAA¹².

Beyond figures, it is evident that although European films reach all three countries examined, contemporary European productions encounter significant barriers to attract audiences. Part of this difficulty seems to arise from the dominance of American films in the box office. These films are distributed by US distribution companies, the majors, which, backed up by Hollywood studios, prioritise blockbusters and other commercially appealing films, invest heavily in promotion and have an extensive occupation strategy, releasing multiple copies and taking a significant portion of the screens in a predatory manner that can't be matched by independent distributors.

Screen quotas for national films in place, both in Brazil and Argentina, further restrict the opportunities for screenings of European films in these countries. Exacerbating the situation, exhibitors tend to favor franchises and blockbusters to attract a perceived guaranteed audience, additionally limiting the exhibition space for films from other countries. As a consequence, independent distributors that normally handle non-mainstream films (European titles, for instance) have difficulty finding a theatrical window of exhibition for their releases.

Although available data is limited, a similar pattern worth highlighting can be detected outside the theatrical market. Brazil and Mexico have well established commercial television companies that maintain their market dominance despite all the changes in the audiovisual sector. Mexican owned Televisa (now TelevisaUnivision) and Brazilian owned Grupo Globo, are vertically integrated conglomerates that take part in both production and distribution activities, generating most of what they broadcast. While Argentina doesn't have a large national television company, its audience also favours domestic content. As a result, broadcasters in the region have little interest in showcasing European cinema. Despite the fact that some European channels including European films are available either on pay cable or satellite TV bundles in all three countries, such as Europa Europa, Eurochannel, France 24, TVE Internacional, Rai DW and RTP International, to name a few, their viewership numbers remain modest.

¹² INCAA provides a list of films exhibited each year, which can be accessed through [this link](#). Using this list in conjunction with the Lumiere database to determine the country of origin, it is possible to estimate that 102 European films and 117 US films were exhibited in Argentina in 2023. However, because institutions can classify the country of origin of coproduced films differently, making accurate comparisons and assessments regarding the number of films per country and their respective market shares remains challenging.

On the other hand, video-on-demand (VOD) services have a strong presence in the region, driven by US-based global streamers, such as Netflix, Disney+, Max and Prime Video. The popularity of these services has significantly altered viewing habits and impacted traditional cinema consumption patterns. In Argentina, Netflix was the leading VOD provider in 2023, holding a market share of 35,8%, followed by Disney+ (15,4%), Max (13%) and Star+ (12,8%) ([Obitel, 2024](#)). In Brazil, despite limited data, Globoplay (Grupo Globo), seemed to surpass Netflix in number of subscriptions, boasting 30 million users¹³ during 2023. Nevertheless, Netflix was still the leading service when it came to market share with 28.5%; Globoplay had 8.7%. In the case of Mexico, Netflix maintained a market share of 53% while Disney+ and Max experienced growth in 2023, reaching 13.5% and 11.8%, respectively. Meanwhile, ViX+ (TelevisaUnivision) emerged as a significant competitor, quadrupling its market share to 7%.

Findings from the interviews

All three markets considered share similarities but also present distinct differences when it comes to the circulation of European films in their territory. Through 46 interviews with film professionals (16 from Argentina, 16 from Brazil, and 14 from Mexico), conducted from September 2023 to October 2024, key insights have emerged regarding the challenges and opportunities encountered within the circulation of European cinema in these countries.

a. The existence of important non-commercial circuits

“European cinema is highly sought after and prestigious. We not only have the Cannes Film Week, which obviously features European films, along with films from other countries, but here in Argentina, we also have the French Cinema Week, the Italian Cinema Week, and the German Cinema Week. It’s very common to see European films in various cycles or settings. Particularly, there is a very eager art film circuit, including director retrospectives” (Argentinian policymaker).

In Argentina, Brazil and Mexico there are two primary channels for the circulation of European films. There’s a non-commercial circuit intertwined with diplomatic efforts, by European embassies and cultural institutions, organizing events like European film weeks, film festivals and exhibitions, which have symbolic importance. There is also a commercial circuit, which, post-pandemic, faces notable hurdles in showcasing European films.

¹³ See es.statista.com/grafico/29404/servicios-de-streaming-con-mas-suscriptores-en-america-latina/

Neither Globoplay nor Netflix release official numbers of its subscribers. Globoplay is estimated to have 30 million users, including unpaid ones. See www.bloomberglinea.com.br/2023/02/23/guerra-do-streaming-globoplay-desafia-netflix-pela-lideranca-do-mercado/

While non-commercial initiatives are important to disseminating European films and culture, they don't seem to translate into a significant increase in the circulation of European films within the commercial circuit. Contemporary European cinema (particularly non-mainstream films) seems to be mostly confined to specialised arthouse or independent outlets, film festivals, a few pay cable and satellite TV channels and platforms like MUBI that focus on independent films. Notable exceptions include European films attaining international acclaim by securing prestigious festival awards and films that have a partnership either with Hollywood studios or a transnational VOD service, as they are likely to be exhibited.

A notable initiative worth highlighting, since it combines commercial and non-commercial aspects and players, is the Tour de Cine Frances in Mexico, the world's most important traveling French film festival according to Unifrance¹⁴. This itinerant french film festival was created nearly three decades ago in a partnership between Mexican distributor Nueva Era Films, the Cinepolis exhibition chain, the French Embassy and Mexico's Alliances Françaises network. This particular festival differs from others in the region for its reach which goes beyond the main capital cities, travelling to 73 cities in Mexico and 15 cities in Central America (Costa Rica, El Salvador, Guatemala, Honduras, Nicaragua) and for its selection which prioritise commercial French films that don't reach Mexico rather than via independent or festival-oriented films. In 2023 the event had an audience of 253.000 spectators while in 2018 it reached an unprecedented 420,000 viewers ([Unifrance 2024](#)).

b. The enduring challenges of commercial circuits

While audiences in all three countries enjoyed European cinema in the past, and classic French, German, Italian and Spanish filmmakers are esteemed among cinephiles, existing data reveals that contemporary European films struggle to secure an exhibition space in theaters as well as in other windows of exhibition. Among the main reasons mentioned by interviewees are the following:

- High risk for distributors

"In the markets and festivals where we all meet, generally, all Latin American distributors know each other, we have very good relationships, and we form alliances. In fact, we form alliances with Argentine and Brazilian distributors to buy the rights for all of Latin America and have more reasonable prices, with lower risk" (Mexican film distributor).

¹⁴ See: <https://en.unifrance.org/news/16986/28e-tour-de-cine-frances-the-world-s-most-important-traveling-french-film-festival>

Latin American distributors carry a high risk when acquiring rights of European films. European films' prices are often high when converted into local currency while ticket prices are comparatively low. As a result, distributors need to sell more tickets in their local market to cover costs. Given that European films usually don't draw large crowds or run for extended periods in theatres, distributors frequently struggle to make a profit. In the case of Argentina, the country's economic instability exacerbates the situation, with the steep devaluation of the local currency often preventing distributors from purchasing films at high prices for the local market or fulfilling payment obligations to European counterparts. The country's implementation of non-tariff trade barriers and import restrictions complicates the acquisition process for foreign films, including cultural services and copyright fees. In addition, independent distributors lack sufficient capital for extensive promotional activities, limiting the visibility of these films.

Some independent distributors across the region are attempting to overcome these limitations by establishing partnerships to acquire films with rights across Latin America, subsequently dividing distribution responsibilities based on their respective territories. This collaborative approach enables them not only to buy films at a better overall price compared to individual rights purchased for each distributor's respective region, and enhance their leverage when negotiating with film producers but also to use digital aggregators to commercialise films to niche streaming services, expanding the reach of these productions in the region. It also allows for the possibility of selling the film to a global streaming service, which is more inclined to buy from a local distributor that holds regional rights.

Remarkably, although independent distributors in Mexico go through the same hurdles, they benefit from the existence of Cineteca Nacional in Mexico City. This space focuses mainly on independent and European cinema and has earned a loyal following among the city's cinephiles, as reflected in its consistently high ticket sales. Unlike traditional commercial cinema chains, like Cinopolis and Cinemex, the Cineteca offers prolonged runs of eight weeks for every film, providing an extended opportunity for these films to reach a wider audience.

- Limited support programmes

(Support programs for distribution) *"needs to be less bureaucratic, because you have to create impressive dossiers... and then when it's approved, you're granted the help. Then, it's another issue, you have to send a lot of paperwork, etc. And the amounts are very small. So, we're all fighting over a smaller and smaller pot"* (Mexican film distributor).

Support programs for the distribution and promotion of European films are available, often contingent on certain national film institutions (e.g., French films benefit from incentives provided by Unifrance, German films receive support from German Films). However, interviewees across all

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three countries expressed concerns regarding the complexity and bureaucratic nature of these schemes. In addition, many distributors noted a consistent decline in the financial support offered by these programs over the years. It was also mentioned that payments are often delayed several months after the initial expenditure.

- Concentration of the exhibition

“Theaters or television platforms have ceased to be, due to the way they are organized, a viable alternative for acquiring, for example, a French film, a Latin American film, or even distributing Argentine cinema that is not the most mainstream. With the current market concentration, there is no real opportunity in theatrical exhibition, nor is there a substitute or complement like there once was with DVDs, or as there used to be with certain TV sales in subregions like the Southern Cone—something that would allow us to continue acquiring quality European cinema, quality Latin American cinema, or quality Argentine cinema, which today faces greater challenges in theaters. The dominance of this concentration, and the ongoing trend toward even greater consolidation, has reached a point where support, funding, or incentives are urgently needed for such films to regain the tools they need to reconnect with audiences.” (Argentinian film distributor).

The exhibition sector in all three countries is highly concentrated, with foreign players dominating the sector in Brazil and Argentina and two local exhibitors taking 97% of the market in Mexico. These big multiplex chains prioritise Hollywood blockbusters, limiting the space for European films in all three countries. As a consequence, European films, particularly independent or non-mainstream, are limited to independent cinemas or relegated to film festivals or thematic weeks. Independent exhibitors mentioned the importance of Europa Cinemas Mundus, a programme that provided support for the exhibition of European films from 2011 to 2013. They emphasized that a similar initiative would help them remain viable and allocate more space in their programming for non-mainstream films, including European productions.

- Scarce media coverage

“Distribution has always been difficult. There have always been significant investments in marketing for big films. However, thanks to the support of the press, there was an important space in Brazil for non-Hollywood cinema. After the pandemic, this space has drastically diminished. Today, the main need in Brazil’s non-Hollywood film market is to create a media outlet, both print and online, dedicated to cinema and capable of generating constant public interest.” (Brazilian film exhibitor and distributor).

It was noted by interviewees in Brazil and Argentina that the press has ceased its coverage of cinema showtimes and reduced the number of critics' reviews of non-mainstream films. This absence of traditional media coverage diminished even more the avenues through which non-blockbuster films were previously promoted and is believed to have a direct impact on their discoverability and potential consumption.

- Growing importance of streaming services

“Basically, the other problem we face is that many platforms and TV networks only buy rights for all of Latin America, while we only have the rights for the Southern Cone. This makes it impossible to sell a film to a major platform. Even if we had rights for all of Latin America, most of these major platforms are very difficult to access, to pitch material, have it evaluated, and get it purchased. It's very hard for a distributor, acting alone, to sell to a major platform, even with rights for all of Latin America. As a result, we're practically limited to theatrical exploitation, which comes with its own challenges and limitations.” (Argentinian film distributor)

The theatrical performance of European films has been significantly impacted by the rise of streaming services. In all three countries, while European titles are present on different streaming offerings, their representation is largely confined to films from France, Spain, and, occasionally, Germany. As a result, smaller productions struggle to be featured. Furthermore, global streaming services such as Netflix, Max or Prime, usually bypass local distributors, buying European films directly from sales agents. MUBI engages with local distributors but offers low prices. In the case of local streaming services operated by national cinema institutes, like Cine.Ar Play in Argentina and Nuestro Cine in Mexico (Brazil is planning to launch its own service, Tela Brasil, in the first trimester of 2025), their focus is primarily on domestic productions, while those owned by local broadcasters, such as Globoplay (Grupo Globo) and Vix (TelevisaUnivision), prioritize their own content, typically excluding European films.

The one exception seems to be content aggregators, such as Sofa Digital in Brazil, that resell niche content to smaller VODs, aiding in this way European film distribution. These services are one of the few willing to buy European films from local distributors in the region. It is also worth noting that during the pandemic some local independent distributors in Brazil launched their own VOD services to promote their catalogues. Most services didn't survive, but their attempts highlight the limited visibility of non-mainstream films in general and European productions in particular.

c. Shortcomings of coproduction agreements

"These coproduction agreements need to be renewed because they are very outdated, considering a reality that has changed a lot. If you look at, for example, the Brazil-Italy Coproduction Agreement from the 1970s, it doesn't make sense. In light of this changing reality, it is necessary to restructure it." (Brazilian film producer and director).

Some professionals emphasized that several co-production agreements with European countries are outdated, failing to address the current needs of the audiovisual industry and its professionals, thereby hindering collaboration. Finding information about coproduction agreements and grants available for non European professionals from each European country is also challenging. They suggested that aggregating and centralizing the information available would make it easier to access and understand requirements.

Policy recommendations

Despite its limited scope, the preliminary findings of this study have several policy implications that require further consideration for action.

- 1) Reboot support programs:** Taking into account the difficulties outlined by interviewees when it comes to distributing and exhibiting European films in Latin America, reviving programs such as the Europa Cinema Mundus, which used to offer support for theatrical programming based on circulation and exchange between MEDIA countries and non-MEDIA member states, should be considered. The MEDIA Mundus program, which existed between 2011-2013, also had lines focused on distribution, promotion and even co-production with countries outside of Europe and it was highly regarded amongst Latin America professionals. Furthermore, current support programs for the distribution and promotion of European films could be reviewed and restructured to simplify the complexity and administrative burden involved in accessing funding, which can deter participation, especially of small players, and hinder the efficient use of resources. Streamlining application procedures and providing clear, user-friendly guidelines would significantly improve the accessibility of these programs for distributors. Moreover, a more predictable and timely payment system should be introduced to ensure that distributors can plan and execute promotional activities effectively.
- 2) Revise and modernize co-production agreements:** As mentioned, the vast majority of interviewees highlighted the importance of coproduction agreements for the internationalization of films and knowledge exchange between different countries. Due to the fact that a significant number of co-production agreements date back to the 1990s or early

2000s, making them outdated and in need of revision, to ensure the alignment with contemporary industry practices it would be useful to revise and change agreements currently in place.

- 3) **Consolidate and centralize information:** Information about coproduction agreements with European countries and existing support schemes is often scattered and fragmented across multiple websites, institutions and countries. As a consequence, it can be hard for foreign film professionals to find the correct data and understand the requirements, especially considering that resources are also in different languages. A central database with all the content would ensure easy accessibility and facilitate better access to resources and possibilities of exchange across countries.
- 4) **Explore partnerships with publicly managed windows of exhibition:** Reflecting on ways of leveraging possible cooperation between publicly managed windows of exhibition, such as Cineteca National in Mexico, Cine Gaumont in Argentina or CineSesc in Brazil, could be beneficial to increase the circulation of European films in these markets. These institutions already assign and give prominence to independent and arthouse films in their programs and tend to exhibit more European films than commercial chains. Greater support with issues such as exhibition rights, dubbing and subtitling, could enhance the presence and visibility of European films. The same would apply to publicly managed streaming services such as CINE.AR Play and Nuestro Cine. While these services prioritise national films, a partnership could foster the circulation and exchange of titles, giving European films another window of exhibition while possibly opening a window for Latin American productions in the EU.

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Policy Brief

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Lessons from the past: European film industry looks back at thirty years of paradoxes

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This policy brief is aimed at:

- EU policy-makers
- national authorities
- industry stakeholders

Introduction

As part of the broader European REBOOT project, researchers from Ghent University and Complutense University of Madrid examined how senior professionals in the European film industry (EFI) look back at thirty years of changes. While the important *Nostradamus* reports (see Koljonen, 2023, 2024) tend to glance in the future of the industry, this research looked backwards: it covers the trends, tensions, and paradoxes in the development of the EFI over the past thirty years.

Using oral history methodologies, the two research teams conducted 68 interviews with senior professionals from various segments of the industry. These include representatives from film production, distribution, exhibition, and policy, as well as a broader 'other' category including film critics, journalists, festival personnel, etc. The report prioritises testimonies on historical shifts in the film and audiovisual industries across three types of territories: a regional focus on the Belgian region of Flanders, a national perspective centred on Spain's major film industry, and a pan-European overview of broader trends. This study is grounded in these key witnesses' personal memories and experiences, offering a unique perspective on how the EFI has evolved. They cover their experiences with digitization, their evaluation of policies implemented in Europe, their perspectives on the rise of streaming platforms and how do they perceive the impact these changes the EFI's competitiveness, both regionally and globally.

Interviewees' reflections: diagnosis of a transformation

While we acknowledge the **need for a more holistic approach** regarding European film policy, our report focused on key segments of the EFI separately. Due to its bottom-up approach, the report has generated a rich set of opinions and recommendations, while it recognized key challenges in the stakeholder's evaluation of the last thirty years. The challenges identified in each of the key segments of the EFI are first summed up separately before the brief provides eight general policy recommendations that connect concerns in all these areas (production, distribution, exhibition and policy).

The interviewees highlighted several critical themes regarding changes in European film **production**. Technological advancements, particularly digitization, have democratized production and fostered creative innovation but also intensified **overproduction**, which many see as

unsustainable and detrimental to competitiveness. **The rise of private broadcasters and global streaming platforms has reshaped funding**, with streamers introducing new financial opportunities but also eroding creative autonomy and shifting focus toward commercially driven series over independent films. **Atomization**, marked by numerous small production companies **persists as a structural weakness**, while market consolidation threatens mid-tier producers, risking cultural diversity. **Hollywood's dominance continues to challenge European cinema**, though some view it as an impetus for resilience. Additionally, tensions arise around the evolving role of producers, who increasingly act as service providers within centralized models favouring global conglomerates.

The main issues in film **distribution** focus on the profound impact of digitization, leading to democratized access and expanded audience reach, but also **heightened competition** and **market oversaturation**. Another key issue is the **difficulty of European films to penetrate transnational borders**. When European films penetrate markets in other regions, they tend to be in the form of co-productions with other countries. The market penetration of European films is heavily concentrated within Europe itself, with 92% of admissions occurring there in 2023. Of these, 68% are in their national markets, leaving only 23% for intra-European exports and a declining 8% in non-European markets (EAO, 2023). **Consolidation among major players has intensified financialization**, concentrating power in multinational corporations while sidelining independent distributors who have great difficulties to survive or rely heavily on public subsidies and niche markets. **Streaming platforms have disrupted traditional distribution by monopolizing high-profile content**, emphasizing marketing, and favouring global over local cultural narratives, yet also offering innovative opportunities for collaboration. **Geo-blocking remains a contentious but vital mechanism** to preserve cultural diversity and regional market dynamics, with its removal potentially threatening Europe's localized film ecosystems.

Related to film **exhibition**, the main issues highlighted by the interviewees revolve around the profound transformations in the cinema exhibition sector due to digitization, **changing audience behaviours**, and the rise of streaming platforms. Key themes include the democratization and oversaturation of content driven by digital flexibility, which has created challenges in sustaining smaller or independent films amid a **"winner-takes-all" market**. The communal and immersive experience of cinema remains vital, especially in attracting younger audiences, with cinemas increasingly focusing on event-based and premium experiences to differentiate themselves. Multiprogramming has allowed for more tailored, diverse programming, but **shorter theatrical runs challenge traditional audience-building**.

When we asked our interviewees about the state of European film **policy**, most interviewees stressed that it remains crucial for the existence of a so called “European cinema”. However, there are several key issues that need to be addressed in future film policy. These include the **overproduction of films**, which strains resources and market capacity; the **limited circulation of European films** within the internal market, which hampers cultural exchange and economic viability; and the **bureaucratic inefficiencies** in funding processes that create barriers for smaller producers and slow down innovation. Additionally, there is a need to balance **cultural diversity with industrial competitiveness**, ensuring that policies support both artistic expression and economic sustainability. The interviewees also stress the importance of **transparency and responsiveness** in policy implementation, particularly in addressing the evolving needs of the film industry and fostering long-term, sustainable collaborations across Europe. Finally, the interviewees underscore the necessity of shifting more focus to **supporting distribution and promotion** to enhance the visibility and success of European films globally.

Policy recommendations

1) An overarching, perhaps unsurprising, recommendation, is a call for more robustly financed support mechanisms. This appeal applied across all levels; supranational, national, and regional.

Against usual criticism, we want to highlight how most respondents stressed the immense challenges faced by an industry that, over the past three decades, has successfully transitioned from a ‘sector’ to a fully-fledged industry, effectively utilizing the limited budgets provided by public institutions. Interviewees stressed that if European policymakers accept or recognize that cinema is valuable in terms of its cultural impact, economic value, and job creation, they need to respond by structurally strengthening support.

2) Improve data collection and market transparency. To address the lack of insight into audience preferences, European policymakers should require streaming platforms operating in Europe to share anonymised audience data with EU institutions and independent distributors. This would enable smaller stakeholders to compete effectively by aligning their strategies with solid market intelligence.

Establishing a centralised European hub for audience data would further improve transparency by aggregating data on viewing behaviour, film circulation and market performance. While the EAO is an extremely effective institution, there is a call for a more fine-grained understanding of audience behaviours and preferences. Such measures would complement existing policies such as the

Audiovisual Media Services Directive (AVMSD, Article 13),¹⁵ which promotes European productions, and the Digital Services Act (DSA), which emphasises the accountability of platforms. Incorporating these new requirements would modernise the policy framework to meet the demands of a data-driven digital economy.

- 3) Strengthen distribution and promotion. There is a need to move beyond supporting film production and to focus on strengthening initiatives related to exhibition, distribution, and promotion of European films. Attention should be directed toward initiatives that enhance co-productions, cross-border circulation, and the distribution of films made in the EU and Europe and thus address the question of overproduction through stronger collaboration among partners and sectors.**

To improve the visibility of European films, Creative Europe MEDIA funding should be increasingly allocated to support independent distributors in developing innovative marketing campaigns and cross-border promotions. A Europe-wide promotional initiative could exhibit culturally significant films across festivals, digital platforms, and mainstream media, creating synergies between regional and global markets. Encouraging hybrid distribution models, such as partnerships between streaming platforms and cinemas, could extend the lifespan of European films, ensuring that they reach diverse audiences. Existing provisions under the MEDIA program (cf. Regulation (EU) 2021/818 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 20 May 2021 establishing the Creative Europe Programme (2021 to 2027) and repealing Regulation (EU) No 1295/2013)¹⁶ already support film circulation, but additional targeted investments are essential to strengthen these initiatives and ensure sustained visibility for European productions.

- 4) Protect cultural diversity through strategic regulation. The preservation of cultural diversity in the EFI hinges on maintaining territorial exclusivity through geo-blocking. Retaining the exemption for audiovisual content under the Geo-blocking Regulation (EU**

¹⁵ The essence of **Article 13(1)** of the AVMSD is to ensure that VOD providers actively contribute to the objective of promoting cultural diversity within the Union by providing a minimum share of European works in their offers. The Commission takes the view that this objective can only be effectively achieved if the 30 % share of European works is secured in each of the national catalogues offered by multi-country VOD providers.

¹⁶ Regulation (EU) 2021/818 establishes the Creative Europe Programme for 2021-2027. It aims to safeguard, develop, and promote European cultural and linguistic diversity and heritage, while increasing the competitiveness and economic potential of the cultural and creative sectors, particularly the audiovisual sector. The programme has three strands: Culture, Media, and Cross-sectoral, each with specific priorities to enhance cooperation, innovation, and sustainability across the cultural and creative industries

2018/302)¹⁷ ensures that distributors can sustain localized funding models and maintain market segmentation.

Additionally, strengthening content quotas for European works on streaming platforms—raising the existing AVMSD (Article 13)¹⁸ quota from 30% to 35%—would enhance the prominence of lesser-known European films. These measures would protect regional market dynamics while supporting the EU's cultural objectives, ensuring that Europe's fragmented but vibrant film ecosystem continues to thrive in the face of global competition.

5) Combat piracy on a larger pan-European scale, as this remains a significant threat to the financial stability of the European film industry.

Policymakers should develop a Europe-wide anti-piracy initiative targeting IPTV systems and torrent-based platforms. This initiative could leverage the existing framework of Directive 2004/48/EC¹⁹ on the enforcement of intellectual property rights, combined with the Digital Services Act's provisions on illegal content removal. Public awareness campaigns should accompany these efforts, highlighting the economic and cultural impact of piracy while promoting legal alternatives. Addressing piracy at both the regulatory and societal levels would strengthen the industry's capacity to protect intellectual property and revenue streams, benefiting both large-scale productions and independent filmmakers.

6) Support exhibitors in their new curatorial role and increase audience engagement. Interviewees highlighted how the sustainability of cinema as a cultural and economic institution requires investment in premium experiences and community engagement.

Exhibition funding under Creative Europe MEDIA should enable cinemas to implement high-value features such as IMAX, 4DX, and integrated dining experiences, enhancing their appeal as social and immersive venues. Parallel efforts should focus on youth engagement through educational initiatives under MEDIA or Erasmus+, fostering an appreciation for European cinema among younger demographics. These measures should also prioritize underserved regions, offering grants to improve infrastructure and expand access to diverse cultural content. Building on MEDIA's

¹⁷ Regulation (EU) 2018/302 addresses unjustified geo-blocking and other forms of discrimination based on customers' nationality, place of residence, or place of establishment within the internal market. It aims to ensure the proper functioning of the EU's internal market by preventing such discriminatory practices in online and offline transactions. The regulation prohibits blocking access to websites and re-routing without the customer's consent, and it ensures equal conditions of access to goods and services for all EU customers.

¹⁸ *Ibid.* (footnote 1)

¹⁹ This directive aims to harmonize the laws of the Member States concerning the enforcement of intellectual property rights to ensure a high, equivalent, and homogeneous level of protection in the internal market.

support for cinema networks like Europa Cinemas²⁰, these initiatives would ensure the long-term relevance of cinemas while addressing regional inequalities.

7) The focus on audiences should be integrated in a broader set of initiatives promoting European films and fostering European film culture.

Interviewees mentioned the importance of strengthening the mediation side of film culture, such as promoting cinema literacy in education and encouraging public broadcasters to give as much attention to European films as they do to (mostly Hollywood) blockbusters. Many of these initiatives (e.g., media literacy programs, collaborations with educational institutions) were mentioned during the conversations; the general impression is, however, that they would benefit from a stronger, coordinated support through a more integrated policy. This approach is also crucial in industrial terms, central for creating an environment where people will become more interested in European films than they are today.

8) Accepting that the EFI is a plural reality, EU-policy makers should engage more intensely in a meaningful dialogue which fully considers the professionals' expertise and experiences when developing policies related to the filmed entertainment industries.

Regarding issues like windowing or the potential abandonment of geo-blocking, the interviewees were largely unanimous in their view that policymakers' positions often contradicted the EFI's interests and appeared to be influenced by GAFAs (Google, Apple, Facebook and Amazon) and other powerful lobby groups. Policy guidelines should thus accept that **Europe's film industry shouldn't mirror that of the USA and its concerns**, and recognize, as one interviewee who worked as a lobbyist in Brussels pointed out, that Europe and the EU are "a union of different markets"; he also added that "despite the dominance of big studios, European audiences are increasingly going to the cinema and consuming more content." It's about acknowledging that, much like Europe's food, beverage, fashion, and other cultural industries, the EFI is a "milky way" made up of a multitude of producers, distributors, and exhibitors.

²⁰ Europa Cinemas is the first network of cinemas focusing on European films. Created in 1992 at the initiative of a group of thirty cinema exhibitors, it has become in 30 years a network of 1,302 cinemas and 3,192 screens in 39 countries. Its main objectives are to provide operational and financial support to cinemas that undertake to give a significant part of their screenings to non-national European films and to put in place activities for young audiences.

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